

SIMPLE GEOMETRICAL MODELS FOR YOUNG'S MODULUS
OF FIBROUS AND PARTICULATE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The concept of fibres in a uniform square array is used to develop a simple model for the transverse modulus of a unidirectional composite. The model defines in a direct way the upper and lower bounds on transverse modulus at a fixed fibre volume fraction, expressing them in terms of equivalent fibres of square cross-section. Modulus values between these bounds are accommodated by a single disposable parameter P , the "relative volume fraction", easily understood as measuring the effective contribution to stiffness from the outer portions of a fibre. The model is more flexible than the frequently used Reuss model.

The model is further developed to embrace particulate composites, upper and lower bounds being defined for the modulus of a cubic array of spherical particles dispersed in a continuous phase. The same disposable parameter as above is used for purposes of fitting to data. Application of both models is illustrated by comparing their predictions with measured moduli for a series of cast polyester/urethane-acrylate blends, and for a series of unidirectional glass-fibre composites with those blends as matrices.

KEYWORDS: Fibre composites; Particulate composites; Young's modulus; Micromechanics; Geometrical model.

1. INTRODUCTION

In studying the mechanical behaviour of unidirectional fibre composites transverse to the fibre direction, or that of particulate composites comprising a continuous and a discontinuous phase, it is often necessary to estimate the value of the appropriate Young's modulus from the elastic properties and proportions of the constituent phases.

This paper presents a simple geometrical approach developed from the square-array model used by Kies (1) in his treatment of stress-concentrations in the matrix of a fibre composite. This will be described as the "series/parallel" (SP) model. Fibres of square cross-section are assumed, and it will be shown that this enables one to determine directly the upper and lower bounds of transverse Young's modulus for a (round-) fibre composite of specified volume fraction. A disposable parameter P , understandable as the "relative volume fraction" of reinforcement, enables the model to be fitted to experimental moduli within this range.

With reference to particulate composites, the above approach leads directly to an expression for the modulus of an array of cubical particles of discontinuous phase (D) in a continuous matrix (C). As with the fibre composite model, a "relative volume fraction" can be employed to fit experimental data. This solution is simpler than a previously-published generalised method for particles of any shape (2). Indeed, the models described here are so straightforward that it would be surprising if no-one had used them before. However, an extensive search of the literature (3) showed no record of their application to fibre composites.

2. THE SP MODEL FOR FIBRE COMPOSITES

2.1 Basis of the model Figure 1 shows at A and B, two views of a unidirectional composite, of unit length in the fibre direction, with fibres arranged in a square array. The transverse section, A, shows the standard model used by Kies (1). In arriving at his concept of strain magnification factor, Kies considered extension under a transverse force, shown by the arrows, F. He compared the matrix strain along lines AB and CD, assuming them to remain equal in length. The shape of the fibres, and in particular, matrix strains along load lines other than AB and CD were ignored.

For the present purpose, this means that it is no more inaccurate to represent the composite by the "square-fibre" model shown below at C and D in the Figure. The only quantitative difference is in the relationship between the fibre-width dimension, or "equivalent square-fibre size", x , and the fibre volume fraction V_f . The square-fibre model has the advantage of emphasising that in the load direction the composite is made up of parallel strips of two types (Figure 1C):

(i) Duplex strips such as abef, in proportion by volume: x , with modulus E_s (see below).

(ii) Matrix-only strips, such as bcde in Figure 1C, in proportion by volume: $(1-x)$, with modulus E_m .

With the usual assumptions of perfect fibre/matrix bonding and identical Poisson ratios, the rule of mixtures gives for the composite transverse modulus:

$$E_t = E_s \cdot x + E_m \cdot (1 - x) \quad (1)$$

The modulus E_s can genuinely be evaluated by the Reuss or equal-stress model to be:

$$E_s = E_m / (1 - (1-R) \cdot x) \quad (2)$$

where: $R = E_m/E_f$, and E_f is the transverse modulus of the fibre.

Substituting for E_s in (1), we can express the ratio of composite transverse modulus to matrix modulus:

$$E_t/E_m = x / (1 - x(1 - R)) + (1-x) \quad (3)$$

It is apparent from Figure 1 that the variable x must lie between 0 and 1. At $x = 0$, $E_t/E_m = 1$, and at $x = 1$, $E_t/E_m = 1/R = E_f/E_m$, as required.

It may be noted in passing that the corresponding modulus ratio using the Reuss model is:

$$E_t/E_m = 1 / (1 - V_f(1 - R)) \quad (4)$$

Here, the fibre shape is ignored, and its volume fraction only considered. Thus, for a given system there is no possibility of variation in the predicted E_t/E_m for a given V_f .

2.2 Upper and lower bound solutions for circular fibres Since reinforcing fibres commonly have a near-circular cross-section, the most useful aspect of the SP model lies in its providing simple and obvious upper and lower bounds to the modulus, for fibres of a given volume fraction.

These bounds are illustrated in Figure 2. For a circular fibre of diameter d in a square array, the volume fraction is:

$$V_f = (\pi/4) \times d^2 \quad ** \quad (5)$$

This is common to all three composites illustrated in Figure 2. The maximum possible modulus would be achieved if the fibres were equivalent to square fibres of side xU (Figure 2C), where:

$$xU = d = \text{SQR}(4V_f/\pi) \quad (6)$$

Similarly, for the lower bound we may take as a model the inscribed square (Figure 2A), for which:

$$xL = d/\text{SQR}(2) = \text{SQR}(2V_f/\pi) \quad (7)$$

These values may be substituted for x in equation (3) to obtain upper and lower bounds respectively, for the ratio: E_t/E_m at any volume fraction V_f .

It is important to note the limits of applicability of the model. As stated previously, the maximum possible value of x is unity. For the upper bound, it is clear from equation (6) that this limit is reached when $4V_f/\pi = 1$. The highest volume fraction which may be considered is therefore: $V_f = \pi/4 = 0.785$, which corresponds to touching fibres in the square array. The same practical limit must be applied to the range of equation (7) for the lower bound. When $V_f = 0.785$, $xL = 0.707$.

2.3 The relative volume fraction, P The limiting cases discussed above may be generalised by expressing the equivalent square fibre size x in terms of the fibre volume fraction V_f by the equation:

$$x = \text{SQR}(P \times V_f) \quad (8)$$

where P is a disposable parameter with a value in the range between $(2/\pi)$ and $(4/\pi)$.

The physical significance of P may be understood in the following manner. In the defining equation (Equation 8), substitute the value of V_f for a square array of circular fibres of diameter d (Equation (5)). Rearranging then gives

$$P = x^2 / ((\pi/4) \times d^2) \quad (9)$$

so that P is the ratio of the cross-sectional area of the equivalent square fibre to that of the actual fibre. Since for prismatic fibres this is also the ratio of the respective volumes, it will be described as the "relative volume fraction".

** Definition of symbols: $\pi = 3.1416$, SQR = square root, CBR = cube root.

The effect of changes in the relative volume fraction as P varies between its limits is illustrated in Figure 2. At the lower limit, $P = 2/\pi$, (Figure 2A), we may consider that the four segmental "lobes" of fibre surrounding the inscribed square, contribute nothing to the stiffening of the matrix. Figure 2C illustrates the upper limit, $P = 4/\pi$, where the equivalent square-fibre size X_u is equal to d . In this case, the four triangular "lobes" of matrix surrounding each fibre constitute an effective lateral extension of the fibre itself. For intermediate values of P, the model appears as in Figure 2B. Evidently, the "physical interpretation" of the model must not be pushed too far. However, it may be seen that P can quantify the effect on transverse modulus of interactions around the periphery of the fibre.

3. THE SP MODEL FOR PARTICULATE COMPOSITES.

3.1 Basis of the model The above treatment leads naturally to the consideration of a particulate composite as a regular array of particles of the discontinuous phase D (modulus E_d) in a matrix of the continuous phase C (modulus E_c). Figure 3 illustrates the model. By analogy with Figure 1, A in Figure 3 represents an array of spherical particles, while B is a sectional view in the plane perpendicular to A. C shows a view, parallel to the load direction FF, of an array of cubical particles. The corresponding sectional view, D, shows that in the load direction, the composite comprises two sets of strips in parallel, one duplex and the other single-phase. In this case we have:

(i) Duplex strips, (pqrs) in proportion by volume: x^2 , with modulus E_s (see below).

(ii) Matrix-only strips, (being the area surrounding pqrs, out to ABCD), in proportion by volume: $(1-x^2)$, with modulus E_c .

Thus, in place of equation (1) we have:

$$E = E_s \cdot x^2 + E_c(1 - x^2) \quad (10)$$

where E is the overall modulus of the composite. With the change of symbols, equation (2) becomes:

$$E_s = E_c / (1 - x(1 - R')) \quad (11)$$

where $R' = E_c/E_d$. The ratio of composite modulus to modulus of the continuous phase is then given by:

$$E/E_c = x^2 / (1 - x(1 - R')) + (1 - x^2) \quad (12)$$

3.2 Relative volume fraction, and bounds In this case, x can be related to the volume fraction of discontinuous phase, V_d , by an expression of the form:

$$x = CBR(P' \cdot V_d) \quad (13)$$

where P' is a disposable parameter as before. As above, P' may be shown to be a "relative volume fraction", since it is the ratio: (volume of equivalent cubical particles) / (volume of spherical particles). For spherical particles of diameter d we have:

$$V_d = (\pi/6) \cdot d^3 \quad (14)$$

Substituting in Equation 13 and rearranging:

$$P' = x^3 / ((\pi/6).d^3) \quad (15)$$

which accords with the above definition.

Upper and lower bounds on composite modulus are established as follows. For the upper bound we use the circumscribed cube, for which $x = x_U = d$, the particle diameter, and since, from Equation (14)

$$d = CBR(6.Vd/\pi) \quad (16)$$

we have, from (13) and (16), the upper bound value:

$$P'(U) = 6/\pi = 1.91 \quad (17)$$

For the lower bound, using the cube inscribed in the sphere, we obtain:

$$x = x_L = d/(\text{SQRT}(3)) \quad (18)$$

whence:

$$P'(L) = 2/(\text{SQRT}(3).\pi) = 0.37 \quad (19)$$

For particulate composites comprising two phases of different moduli we may consider each in turn to be continuous. Equation (12) then gives two different curves for E as a function of composition, with appropriate substitutions of E_c and R' .

4. APPLICATIONS OF THE SP MODELS.

These models were developed in connection with an investigation into the use of polymer blends for composite matrices, which is described elsewhere (4,5). A polyester laminating resin with modulus 3.5GPa (PE), was blended with a urethane acrylate of modulus 1GPa (UA), in a range of proportions.

In a study of the constitution of the unfilled matrix resins, the variation of modulus with composition was compared with predictions of the SP particulate model with $P' = 1$ (Figure 4). This provided good corroborative evidence for the existence of a phase inversion in the system, from PE-continuous to UA-continuous, at about 40% UA.

In the same programme, unidirectional composites were made, with nominally constant fibre volume fraction, from a range of the above blends. The variation of transverse Young's modulus with matrix composition is illustrated in Figure 5 (solid symbols). Also shown are the results of calculations to estimate transverse modulus from the measured matrix modulus (Figure 4), using respectively the Reuss model (triangular symbols), and the SP fibre model with $P = 4/(\pi)$, the upper bound (open circles). Neither model comes close to the measured values for the highly flexible UA-rich matrices, where simply the disparity in Poissons ratio between fibre and matrix would invalidate its assumptions. However, over a wide range of compositions among the stiffer composites, more akin to conventional polyester materials, the SP model shows an acceptable measure of agreement.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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6. REFERENCES

1. J A Kies, "Maximum strains in the resin of fibre glass composites". U.S. Naval Research Laboratory Report NRL 5752, 1962.
2. R M Jones, "Mechanics of Composite Materials", McGraw-Hill Kogakusha Ltd, New York, 1985, P97.
3. G M Wells, PhD Thesis, University of Bath. 1987.
4. M A Girardi, PhD thesis, University of Bath, 1991.
5. M A Girardi and M G Phillips, Paper to be presented at ICCM8.

Figure 1. Illustration of the series/parallel (SP) model for fibre composite transverse modulus.

- A. Section parallel to load direction FF , showing conventional square array of round fibres, diameter d . For AB , CD , see text.
- B. View perpendicular to load direction, showing unit length of the model in the fibre direction.
- C. Section parallel to load direction FF , showing square fibres of width X , in a square array. Model may be considered as parallel strips in the load direction: matrix only, $bcde$; duplex, $abef$.
- D. As B, above.

Figure 2. Transverse sectional views of a composite with round fibres of diameter d , showing a range of "equivalent square-fibre sizes" x . These correspond to the following values of transverse modulus:

A. Lower bound, with the section of the equivalent square fibre inscribed in the circle. $x = x_L = d/(\text{SQR}(2))$.

B. An intermediate case.

C. Upper bound, with the section of the equivalent square fibre circumscribed around the circle. $x = x_U = d$.

Figure 3. Illustration of the series/parallel (SP) model for modulus of particulate composites.

A. View parallel to load direction FF showing cubic array of spherical particles.

B. Section perpendicular to load direction, showing unit width of the model.

C. View parallel to load direction FF showing cubic array of cubical particles.

D. Section, perpendicular to the load direction, indicating relative areas of parallel strips in the load direction: duplex, pqr; matrix only, the remainder within ABCD.

Figure 4. Modulus as a function of composition for a series of polyester/urethane acrylate blends. Curves represent SP model with $P = 1$.
A, polyester phase continuous.
B, urethane acrylate phase continuous.
Experimental values from reference 4.

Figure 5. Transverse modulus for unidirectional composites with nominally constant fibre volume fraction, as a function of matrix composition. Matrices are blends of polyester with urethane acrylate (UA). Filled circles are experimental values from reference 4. Open circles show values calculated from the measured matrix moduli of Figure 4 using the SP model with $P = 4/(\pi)$. Triangles show values calculated similarly, but using the Reuss model.